

Deliverable report for

Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement Number 101069888

Deliverable D11.9

“Reports to the European Commission”

Due date of deliverable: 2024/08/31

Actual submission date: 2024/08/31

Identifier:	D11.9: Monitoring and evaluation annual report of communication and dissemination activities (2nd release)
Beneficiaries:	CONSORTIUM
Work package/task:	WP11 / Task 11.2
Document status:	draft / <u>final</u>
Confidentiality:	confidential / restricted / <u>public</u>

This project is funded under Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement no 101069888

Lead beneficiary for this deliverable: CSIC - ITQ

Dissemination Level:			
PU	Defined in the DoW	Public	Yes/No
PP		Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	Yes/No
RE		Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	Yes/No
CO		Confidential, only for partners of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	Yes/No

This project is funded under Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement no 101069888

Contents

1. Abbreviations	4
2. Summary	5
3. Communication and dissemination activities	5
3.1 ALL-IN Zero Website	5
3.2 ALL-IN Zero Social Media.....	6
3.3 ALL-IN Zero Newsletter	7
3.4 ALL-IN Zero Video	8
3.5 Publications in Scientific Journals.....	9
3.6 Presentations at National and International Scientific Conferences.....	9
3.7 Others	10

1. Abbreviations

CO: Confidential

D: Deliverable

GA: Grant Agreement

2. Summary

This document summarizes the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the second year of the European project ALL-IN Zero, relative to task 11.2. It includes links and images of the project website, press clippings, dissemination activities, social networks, etc.

According to the Grant Agreement (GA) this report will be updated and delivered annually within the deliverables D11.8-D11.11 Reports on monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities. This is the second delivery, including all communication and dissemination activities executed from month 12 to month 24.

3. Communication and dissemination activities

3.1 ALL-IN Zero Website

The ALL-IN Zero website allinzero.eu is available from month 6 of the project. The website has been actively maintained and updated during the last 12 months by iPoint (Figure 1). The aim of the website is to increase the visibility and recognition of the ALL-IN Zero project to both, the scientific and industrial communities and the general public.

Google Analytics utilities have been employed from month 12 to month 24 to closely monitor the website activity: number of visitors, duration of the visits, geographical area, most visited sections of the webpage, etc (see Table 1).

Figure 1: ALL-IN Zero website home page

Table 1: Google Analytics Data from 29th August 2023 to 29th August 2024

Event Name	Number of events 3.062 Total	Total users 313 Total	Number of events per user 9,78 average
1. Page view	1.060	313	3.39
2. User engagement	845	203	4,18
3. Session start	503	312	1,61
4. First visit	312	312	1,00
5. Scroll	254	124	2,05
6. File downloads	42	23	1,83
7. Clicks	36	21	1,71
8. Form start	10	10	1,00

3.2 ALL-IN Zero Social Media

Both the [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts for the ALL-IN Zero project have been already created and are being used to publish announcements and relevant information about the project (see Figure 2 and Figure 3). Official Twitter/LinkedIn accounts and groups have joined to raise awareness among potentially interested stakeholders. The visibility of the social media post of the ALL-IN Zero project is shown in Table 2.

Figure 2: ALL-IN Zero Twitter

Figure 3: ALL-IN Zero LinkedIn account

Table 2: Social media visibility from January 2023 to August 2024

Social Media	Posts	Followers	Impressions
Twitter	17	27	>1000
Linkedin	16	152	>18500

3.3 ALL-IN Zero Newsletter

A newsletter will be produced once a year highlighting project results and milestones. Figure 4 shows the second newsletter comprising months 12 to 24 of the project, that has been uploaded to the website.

Figure 4: ALL-IN Zero project second Newsletter

3.4 ALL-IN Zero Video

A video aiming at raising awareness of the project and its expected outcomes has been released (see Figure 5). This video is being used by the partners to present the project, as well as for press relations purposes, considering the general public as the main target audience. This video provides an overview of our goals, the challenges we aim to address, and the positive impact the project is striving to achieve across Europe. The video is accessible from the website ([Link](#)), and it has also been uploaded to YouTube ([Link](#)) and LinkedIn ([Link](#)).

Figure 5: Image from the video of the ALL-IN-Zero project

3.5 Publications in Scientific Journals

The first scientific publication of the project activities and results has been published in a top-ranked scientific journal:

- Desantes, J. M., Novella, R., Lopez-Juarez, M., & Nidaguila, I. (2024). Experimental assessment of a heavy-duty fuel cell system in relevant operating conditions. *Applied Energy*, 376, 124293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.124293>

3.6 Presentations at National and International Scientific Conferences

The partners have presented the project activities and results at national and international conferences during months 12 to 24. Table 3 contains the details of these presentations. The website and the social media of the project also collect these contributions.

Table 3: Summary of the press releases which have disseminated ALL-IN Zero project

Type of Event	Name of Event	Location	Date	Responsibility
Conference	19th Symposium Sustainable Mobility, Transport and Power Generation (LEC 2023)	Graz (Austria)	September 2023	UPV
Conference	Autumn School 2023 - ITQ	Valencia (Spain)	October 2023	CSIC
Conference	XIX Simposio de Jóvenes Investigadores Químicos de la RSEQ Murcia 2023	Murcia (Spain)	November 2023	CSIC
Conference	VI Winter Meeting ITQ	Valencia (Spain)	December 2023	CSIC
Conference	MUBIL EXPO	Gipuzkoa (Spain)	April 2024	AVL-I
Conference	17th International Conference On Inorganic Membranes	Florianópolis (Brazil)	July 2024	FZJ
Conference	17th International Conference On Inorganic Membranes	Florianópolis (Brazil)	July 2024	FZJ
Conference	7th International Workshop "Prospects on Protonic Ceramic Cells" PPCC2024	Dijon (France)	July 2024	CSIC
Conference	24th International Conference on Solid State Ionics	London (United Kingdom)	July 2024	CSIC

3.7 Others

The partners have carried out other dissemination activities during 12 to 24 months that have been summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of the press releases which have disseminated ALL-IN Zero project

Type of Event	Name of Event	Format	Date	Responsibility
Website	CSIC Webpage (ITQ)	Web post	October 2022	CSIC
Magazine	FOCUS AVL Magazine	Magazine	December 2023	AVL
Social media	FZ Jülich Energie und Klima / Energy & Climate	Twitter post	October 2023	FZJ
Social media	Forschungszentrum Jülich - IEK-1	LinkedIn post	October 2023	FZJ
Internal communication	Forschungszentrum Jülich - IEK-1 Colloquium	Presentation	October 2023	FZJ
Internal communication	Forschungszentrum Jülich - IEK-1 Colloquium	Presentation	October 2023	FZJ
Seminar	III Jornada Smart Factory	Round Table	January 2024	UPV
Video	Internal AVL news team channel	Video	March 2024	AVL
Social media	UPV-CMT LinkedIn account	LinkedIn post	April 2024	UPV
Seminar	Workshop on UPV-CMT Research Projects and Facilities	Speech	April 2024	UPV
Newsletter	H2Ports project newsletter	Newsletter	May 2024	UPV
Workshop	SEED, International Conference On Sustainable Energy Education	Presentation	July 2024	CSIC